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Systematic review on concentrated solar power energy

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Abstract:

The renewable energy sources are having a promising future in developing countries like India, where the need of environmental safeguarding and economic development can be met at certain level. Concentrated solar thermal power energy can give solution by means of electricity generation and thermal storage. The increase in demand of energy can be fulfilled by renewable energy power sources. The Government of India has taken initiatives by various policies and projects to use the concentrated solar thermal power energy. The parabolic concentrated collector, power or solar towers are in use nowadays. This research paper is about present situation in India about concentrated solar thermal power energy, with addition of development in strategies to use solar energy solutions effectively.

Keywords:

Renewable energy, Challenges in India, Concentrated solar thermal power energy, Electricity generation, Thermal storage

1. Introduction:

The Sun is vast source of heat and sunlight energy. The solar energy can be utilised in two different ways, one is by photovoltaics and other is by concentrated solar power. In photovoltaics, the electrical energy is generated by using photovoltaics effects cells panel. In concentrated solar power, the electrical energy is generated by heating a working fluid using concentrators and mirrors in a power block. This stored heat in molten salts allows concentrated solar power (CSP) plants to generate electricity, when solar sets having major advantage over photovoltaics (PV) power plants. In developing countries like India about 70% of energy is provided by coal- based power plants. A higher amount of fossil fuels are used to enhance the economy. Consumption of power is increasing in parallel with economic growth in India. The phase of changing from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources will be helpful in increasing efficiency with cogeneration. It may be possible by Year 2050, that the fossil fuels will be replaced by renewable energy. The renewable energy development, improvement in energy efficiency, increase in energy conservation, carbon taxes, more equitable balancing of human well-being, per capita energy use, cap and trade system, carbon capture, utilisation, storage and nuclear power development are the ways by which fossil fuels can be replaced by renewable energy. This research paper is about determining the CSP projects and technologies with respect to present status. The market dynamics, economic feasibility and Government's policies are described. Indian Government has made regulatory framework and policies which is backbone of renewable energy development in India. India is steadily developing country in World after China and fourth largest energy consumption country in the World after China. The Government schemes are such as 24×7 affordable and quality power to all, Pradhan Mantri Sahaj Bijli Har Ghar Yojana which aim to provide uninterrupted electricity to all.

2. Concentrated solar power technology and components:

The main components of CSP are solar field, thermal energy storage (TES) and thermodynamic power block. The sun energy is concentrated on receiver or absorber by reflectors or concentrators. The concentrating solar power is converted to thermal energy by receiver. The working fluid within the power block gets heated due to heat energy emitted by receiver. This generates electricity by direct or indirect method. The advantages of direct method is that the storage medium is used as HTF, so extra heat exchanger is not needed. Water or steam is the HTF medium. The indirect method consists of two different fluids. The HTF and storage medium are the two fluids, so additional heat exchanger is needed. HTF fluids used are molten

salts and heat oil. HTF is an energy storage medium. The economy and reliability can be improved by combination of CSP with TES. The maintenance of balanced supply and demand equilibrium is obtained by mitigation of adverse effects resulting from intermittent nature of renewable energy.

Figure. 1: Schematic of concentrated solar power plant

2.1. Parabolic through collector (PTC):

Parabolic through collector is having most advanced, successful and mature technology. A parabolic concentrator or reflector, an absorber or receiver tube and a focal line are the components of parabolic through collector. The solar field of PTC comprises a significant quantity of linearly interconnected parabolic through collectors. Solar energy is absorbed by continuously aligning with Sun's trajectory. This is achieved by uniaxial tracking mechanism of reflector. So maximum energy is captured within days' time. When solar radiations are directed towards reflector, the radiations are focused on tube of absorber. The solar radiations coming on reflectors are reflected to tube of absorber, thereby increasing temperature of tube. The thermal energy is absorbed by heat transfer fluid (HTF). Thus the HTF converts solar radiations into the latent heat. Solar fields harness the thermal energy, which the power block uses to generate electricity. Mostly the steam Rankine power cycle is used with the PTC due to its suitability to working temperature of around 400°C.

Figure. 2: Parabolic through collector

2.2. Linear fresnel reflector (LFR):

It is the modified version of parabolic through collector system. The solar collector used in solar field is different type in LFR as compared to PTC. The array of mirror strips that can be either linear or curved in shape are used in Linear Fresnel Reflector. The mirror strips acts as reflector, akin to Fresnel lens, concentrating solar radiations on the stationary receiver situated on a linear aligned along the mirror's focal line. Reflectors undergo continuous rotation to track the Sun, so that maximum energy can be utilised and the focus remains fixed on designated receiver. The design simplicity, reduced and running cost over PTC are the advantages of LFR.

Figure. 3: Linear fresnel reflector

2.3. Solar power tower (SPT):

SPT consists of heliostat field, a central housing a receiver and a power block. Number of flat or slightly curved computer controlled mirrors are arranged in solar field. Along the two axes, Sun's trajectory is followed by these mirrors. Due to this solar reflected rays are directed towards central receiver, situated at the centre of solar field of tower. The concentrated rays create high thermal energy. The HTF in central receiver emits heat energy to the heat exchanger's working fluid. This energy transfer powers the thermodynamic cycle and generates electricity from working fluid.

Figure. 4: Solar power tower

2.4. Parabolic disc collector (PDC):

The two axes tracking system is used to focus sunlight in parabolic disc collector. Sun's apparent path in sky is followed by entire system. The focal receiver receives the concentrated solar energy. This is used to power Stirling Engine, a gas turbine cycle or a HTF leading to ground based power plant. The temperature in receiver reaches approximately 1500°C. As compared to other CSP technologies, the PDC has highest optical efficiency, concentration ratio and overall conversion efficiency. Higher initial investment is required and it is not compatible with thermal energy storage or hybridization systems.

Figure. 5: Parabolic disc collector

3. Comparison between solar photovoltaics & concentrated solar power:

The photovoltaic cells are used for converting solar energy of direct sunlight into electricity in solar photovoltaic plants. This method is useful in individual home installation to expansive solar power plants. For inherent storage capability, additional infrastructure is required. On the other hand, concentrated solar power uses mirrors or lenses to concentrate sunlight on receiver, generating high temperature heat that drives steam turbine for electricity generation. Lower initial capital cost and longer operational lifetime is achieved in Concentrated Solar Power as compared to batteries used in Photovoltaic Cells System. The CSP can store excess heat generated during sunny season and convert it to electricity as needed, even after sunset or during cloudy conditions. This feature stabilizes the grid and meets peak demand resulting in use of less fossil fuels. For industrial operation and desalination, the CSP is suited, enhancing the future energy scenario. CSP can deliver dependable and adaptable in conjunction with PV. States like, Madhya pradesh, Gujrat, Ladakh, Maharashtra and Rajasthan have requisite quantity of solar radiations available and can be optimal locations for setting up CSP plants.

4. Recent developments in India:

The CSP operational capability is around 200 MW in India. CSP is major technology, based on PTC, followed by LFR and SPT in solar thermal plants. The latest CSP project based on hybrid LFR technology started in Year 2019 with total capacity of 14 MW in Dadri ISCC plant. Due to availability of maximum sunlight in the state of Rajasthan, higher number of CSP plants are installed. Steam Rankine Cycle is used in CSP to generate electricity. Recently there has been increasing fascination with hybrid CSP/PV/TES power systems. The solar PV/CSP

technologies merges advantages by reducing reliance on expensive batteries. PV panels generates electricity during direct sunlight while CSP technology for its inherent thermal energy storage capability, so even after sunset or low sunlight period, dispatch able power generation is possible. Hybrid CSP/PV is a cost effective solution for grid stability making less reliability on battery storage.

4.1. Factors affecting the selection of CSP in India:

Following are the factors affecting the selection of CSP in India –

1. Technical factors like Technical maturity, Capacity factor and Technology flexibility (Hybridization) and Grid Connection
2. Plant site selection factors like Climate condition and Land, Water availability and Surrounding Environment
3. Economic factors like Capital cost, Operation and Maintenance cost, Electricity cost per unit, Research and Development cost
4. Social factors like Social acceptance, Job creation and Impact on Human health
5. Government initiatives and Foreign Dependency

5. Conclusion:

The dependency on non-renewable energy sources like fossil fuels and carbon emissions can be minimised by using renewable energy sources. In India for eco-friendly agriculture sector renewable solar energy has great potential. India has minimised carbon emissions by 33% to 35% by Year 2030 as compared to Year 2005. In overall power generation capacity, India has decided to utilise 40% by renewable energy sources, as agreed during Paris Climate Conference. Mirrors are used to concentrate and amplify solar radiations in concentrated solar power plants. For generating electricity within expansive power plants the concentrated solar power technology is used. CSP equipped with TES has capacity to store energy, enabling it's utilisation during both day-time and night-time. CSP is a technologically advance and economically viable solution. This can reduce carbon emissions by substituting conventional thermal power plants. Furthermore, Hybrid system can be introduced in India's existing electricity generation infrastructure using CSP. With appropriate Government backing, the CSP can potentially contribute 11.3% of worldwide electricity generation. CSP technologies can be introduced in areas having abundant solar irradiance like Rajasthan, Gujrat and Tamilnadu in

India. CSP introduces promising approach towards achieving sustainable energy production by meeting peak electricity demand while ensuring grid stability with minimising adverse environmental effects.

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